

Terraforming and Constructing Habitats

(Extended 3)

The targets for terraforming and constructing habitats, along with their respective surface areas compared to Earth, the period of time required for terraforming, the number of potentially hosted people, the company involved in the process, and the number of robots and machinery involved are presented in this manuscript.

1. Target: Moon

Surface Area compared to Earth: 0.07

Period of Time (Terraformed): 23rd century

Number of (Potentially) Hosted People: 500M+

Company (involved in the Process of Creating Habitats): Ndoni Advanced Robotics (NAR)

Number of robots and machinery involved in the process of creating habitats: 30M+

2. Target: Mars

Surface Area compared to Earth: 0.38

Period of Time (Terraformed): 25th century

Number of (Potentially) Hosted People: 3B+

Company (involved in the Process of Creating Habitats): Ndoni Advanced Robotics (NAR)

Number of robots and machinery involved in the process of creating habitats: 70M+

3. Target: Saturn

Surface Area compared to Earth: 83

Period of Time (Terraformed): 27th century

Number of (Potentially) Hosted People: 600B+

Company (involved in the Process of Creating Habitats): Ndoni Advanced Robotics (NAR)

Number of robots and machinery involved in the process of creating habitats: 120B+

4. Target: Jupiter

Surface Area compared to Earth: 120

Period of Time (Terraformed): 32nd century

Number of (Potentially) Hosted People: 900B+

Company (involved in the Process of Creating Habitats): Ndoni Advanced Robotics (NAR)

Number of robots and machinery involved in the process of creating habitats: 350B+

5. Target: Solar System

Surface Area compared to Earth: **Unspecified**

Period of Time (Terraformed): 45th century

Number of (Potentially) Hosted People: 50T+

Company (involved in the Process of Creating Habitats): Ndoni Advanced Robotics (NAR)

Number of robots and machinery involved in the process of creating habitats: 500B+

6. Target: Milky Way galaxy

Surface Area compared to Earth: **Unspecified**

Period of Time (Terraformed): Year 1M-1B

Number of (Potentially) Hosted People: 1.6 Sextillion+ (160 Billion Billion)

Company (involved in the Process of Creating Habitats): Ndoni Advanced Robotics (NAR)

Number of robots and machinery involved in the process of creating habitats: 1 Quintillion-1

Septillion

© *Copyright*

Albi Ndoni
Tirana, Albania
03/11/2024